

ON THE ISSUE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECTS ON THE DEVELOPMENT AND PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF KNOWLEDGE IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. Higher education today faces important tasks, such as educating and training the younger generation, capable of actively participating in a qualitatively new, rapidly changing stage of development of society, as well as the implementation of priority projects to prepare students for the mastery and practical application of acquired knowledge in the digital economy.

The article discusses the need to further improve the education system in the context of socio-political modernization of society.

Keywords: education, modernization, reform, human capital, information technology, competitive personnel, cooperation, educational technology.

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda oliy ta'lim oldiga jamiyat taraqqiyotining sifat jihatidan yangi, tez o'zgarib borayotgan bosqichida faol ishtirok eta oladigan yosh avlodni tarbiyalash va tarbiyalash, shuningdek, raqamli iqtisodiyotda talabalarni olingan bilimlarini o'zlashtirish va amaliy qo'llashga tayyorlash bo'yicha ustuvor loyihalarni amalga oshirish kabi muhim vazifalar turibdi. Maqolada jamiyatning ijtimoiy-siyosiy modernizatsiyasi sharoitida ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish zarurligi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, modernizatsiya, islohot, inson kapitali, axborot texnologiyalari, raqobatdosh kadr, hamkorlik, ta'lim texnologiyalari

Аннотация. Перед высшим образованием сегодня стоят важные задачи, такие как воспитание и подготовка молодого поколения, способного активно включаться в качественно новый, стремительно меняющийся этап развития общества, а также реализация приоритетных проектов по подготовке обучающихся к освоению и практическому применению полученных знаний в условиях цифровой экономики. В статье рассматриваются вопросы необходимости дальнейшего совершенствования системы образования в условиях социально-политической модернизации общества.

Ключевые слова: образование, модернизация, инновации, сотрудничество, человеческий капитал, цифровизация, образовательная среда, научный потенциал.

Attention to the field of education is becoming especially relevant throughout the world in the age of globalization and information technology, when the level of development of a country is determined not only by socio-economic, cultural indicators, assessment of strength and power, but is largely based on its intellectual potential. After all, it is scientific and technological progress, the foundations of which are laid in the educational environment, that is the central link in the sustainable development and prosperity of the country.

The issue of modernization of education, the implementation of which could ensure a transition to a new type of social development, is especially acute for Uzbekistan. As is known, modernization is a process of transformation that involves the movement of society towards the most effective model of sustainable development, overcoming economic backwardness, political instability, the development of innovation, the process of creating new technologies, a new system of spiritual values and ideological attitudes.

Modernization of education is a complex multifaceted process, so its implementation should be based on the results of in-depth theoretical research. One of the important issues of modernization of the education system, requiring philosophical analysis, seems to be understanding the problem of the relationship between various aspects in the theory and practice of training specialists in new socio-economic conditions. To do this, it is important to analyze the socio-philosophical foundations of the modernization of education related to the new picture of the world, as well as the place of man in the modern world. This will make it possible to identify directions for the development of vocational education and reach educational technologies that can transform the sphere of education into the sphere of reproduction of a creative personality.

It is quite obvious that this cannot be accomplished without studying the modern educational situation, the basic principles of the evolution of modern education, analyzing new trends and understanding the ways of transition from the philosophical foundations of the development of education to the practice of its reform.

As you know, on January 28, 2022, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev “On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026” was issued [3]. The fourth priority area of this Strategy is the implementation of a fair social policy and the development of human capital. In particular, in solving problems for the further development of this area, it is envisaged to improve the quality of education in schools and raise the knowledge and qualifications of teaching staff to an international level, by: determining domestic or international certification requirements for each subject for conducting activities in a school; diagnosing the knowledge and skills of school teachers who do not have a category; optimization of regional units of the public education system through complete digitalization of their activities, etc.

If we consider that today the urgent need for scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel alone is more than 5000, this figure will increase at least 50–100 times, if we also take into account the urgent need for scientific and pedagogical personnel in the production spheres. The incompatibility of the education system with the needs of the economy is a serious problem today.

According to a World Bank study, 35% of Uzbekistan faces difficulties in finding qualified specialists with higher education.

To implement these national tasks of training specialists abroad and dialogue with compatriots in 2019, it is planned to allocate 45 billion sums (54 million US dollars in equivalent) from the state budget to the «El-Yurt Umidi» Foundation. In the future, this amount will be increased.

Currently, information technology occupies a central place in education: the emergence of various online courses, educational resources and platforms that complement and compete with traditional educational organizations.

Government subsidies and support amount to billions to create and support digital educational platforms, as well as develop and adapt legislative and technical policies and initiatives. Digital tools in higher education are becoming an integral part of domestic and global politics and economics.

Digitalization is also having an impact in the academic sphere. The modern higher education system has gone through an extremely important stage of computerization and informatization. It can be noted that the mechanisms of change in the information space were complex, dependent on funding, on the level of higher educational institutions, on the level of readiness of teaching staff, etc.

Information technology plays a huge role in increasing the efficiency of the education process. Unfortunately, it must be noted that today there remains a low level of use of information technology in the educational sphere, both in terms of expanding access and in terms of the use of new teaching methods.

Measures taken to solve these problems will contribute to the widespread use of ICT tools, allowing for much greater flexibility and lower costs in choosing courses for training and mastering the content of relevant specialties provided by higher education. The introduction of modern educational programs, pedagogical and smart technologies into the educational process will help to radically improve the quality of education. It is obvious that a positive imprint on the quality training of highly qualified specialists will be left by the organization of distance classes and seminars, video conferences, which will also contribute to strengthening interactive interaction and cooperation between educational institutions, including foreign ones

Modern digital technologies, media platforms, and electronic texts are increasingly in demand in education, as they contribute to the realization of educational opportunities, allow for more effective building of the educational process, placing students and teachers at the center of the networked social world. New digital technologies make it possible to solve key educational problems that cannot be solved or are poorly solved on the basis of traditional technologies. Digital technologies provide opportunities to improve the quality of education, the successful functioning of the internal structure of an educational organization, which implies the use of digital resource planning systems, electronic document management. The digital environment of an educational organization requires certain ICT tools that are systematized and meet the requirements of the state standard, which is aimed at more effectively achieving learning outcomes. Effective management of an educational organization assumes that the digital environment should become a common field of interaction for all participants in educational relations, an effective tool for managing the quality of education.

Today, digital educational technologies of massive open online courses have become widespread. Such distance e-learning courses are provided by modern educational organizations for everyone. Such distance e-learning courses are provided by modern educational organizations for everyone. They allow the learner to remotely in any convenient form receive qualified training in a specific narrow area in accordance with his level of knowledge, needs and professional interests.

The digital form of organizing the activities of any educational organization, and therefore a university, becomes a significant indicator that ensures effective functioning, development, competitiveness and relevance. Accordingly, the digital educational environment becomes one of the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of management of an educational organization.

The introduction of digital technologies and digital tools, their use in managing an organization, providing access to digital educational and methodological materials, and expanding the space for creativity contributes to the transition to a model of personalized organization of the educational process.

Digitalization in education is a significant step into the future, but it is obvious that the current stage of digitalization of education will also lead to a change in the traditional appearance and forms of conducting training sessions.

Effective digital transformation is not just about technology. It requires a willingness to embrace technology in new ways beyond the organizational process.

It must be continuous and progressive in order to improve teaching and learning, support existing processes and increase efficiency. The role of the teacher will also change significantly, who will have the opportunity to create their own educational content and form a personal professional profile. As a result of this process, the teacher will turn into a mentor for students, guiding and orienting them within the digital educational space.

An important direction in the education system is the formation of the competitiveness of universities. The main tool for solving this problem is fundamentally new regulatory documents in the field of education (educational standards), which are currently being developed taking into account modern experience in organizing the educational process in leading universities in the world.

When developing new educational standards, the main task is to train modern, highly professional specialists who have the most up-to-date knowledge with analytical and creative thinking, skills in using advanced information and communication technologies and are able to effectively apply all this in their daily practical activities.

The most important area of work in the field of education remains the stimulation of research and innovation activities, the creation of effective mechanisms for introducing scientific and innovative achievements into practice, the creation of scientific and experimental specialized laboratories, high technology centers, and technology parks at higher educational institutions and research institutes.

In conclusion, we can conclude that at the present stage of development, Uzbekistan is successfully solving strategic tasks of modernizing the entire national education system, introducing modern information and communication technologies, creating a digital educational environment, improving the teaching of foreign languages, forming a new system of postgraduate education, as well as development of a system for advanced training and retraining of academic and administrative personnel of universities, etc.

Undoubtedly, the implementation of these strategic objectives will ensure the progressive development of the entire system of lifelong education as a single educational-research-production complex based on state and non-state educational institutions, the formation of a competitive environment in the field of education and training, the openness of the system of lifelong education of the republic in the market of educational services, exchange information and specialists, strengthening the international authority of the educational system of Uzbekistan.

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